

EU SUPPORT FOR NON-PROFIT SECTOR - CASE STUDY¹

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Abstract: This paper examines the impact of funding from the EU budget to non-governmental or nonprofit organizations on their successful establishment in the market. Specifically, this paper focuses on two EU programmes, Erasmus+ and ESC, which are significantly used by nonprofit entities. In addition to the use of statistical data from the European Union, the analysis in this paper also includes a case study of two civic associations operating in eastern Slovakia. Based on data from these nonprofit entities, we could conclude that EU grant programmes form a significant part of the revenue items of nonprofit organizations budgets as it was shown that such grants make up over 97% of the income of both examined Slovak nonprofit organizations.

Key words: EU budget, Erasmus+, European Solidarity Corps, non-government organizations, nonprofit organizations

JEL code: F39, L31

INTRODUCTION

The nonprofit sector and its organisations are very widely defined as different countries, and cultures use different terms for describing them. One of the most commonly used definition for the nonprofit sector was settled by Salamon and Anheier (1992, p. 1) and supplemented by Dobrai and Farkas (2016, p. 26), who define nonprofit organisations as the ones that are

- formally constituted, meaning that they are institutionalised;
- non-governmental in primary structure, meaning that even though they receive support from the government are still independent of it and private;
- self-governing, meaning that are controlled by authorities within the organisation such as the Board of Supervisors;

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- non-profit-distributing, meaning that all profits made are reinvested back to the organisation to fulfil its goals, vision and mission and
- voluntary, which means providing voluntary membership or offering voluntary participation in the organisation's activities.

Generally, we can include non-governmental organisations (NGOs) among nonprofit organisations. Unerman and O'Dwyer (2006, p. 307) understand them as all organisations that are neither governmental organisations, meaning that they are not part of the public sector, but also not private, meaning for-profit or commercial organisations. Lewis (2009, p. 1) also points out, based on these definitions, that the term "non-governmental organisations" is widely used, often overlapping with terms such as "nonprofit organisations", "voluntary organisations" or "civil society organisations".

Lewis (2009, p.1) and the European Commission (2020) also point out that NGOs are currently recognised as key players in the third sector in the social field.

Based on these facts, we state that the nonprofit sector is a significant part of the life of all individuals, whether consciously or unconsciously. In the following sections of this paper, we will look at the EU budget as a source of funding for NGOs. Specifically, we describe two EU programmes using descriptive statistics, namely the Erasmus+ Programme and the European Solidarity Corps, at the European and local levels. In the 4th chapter of this paper, we have prepared a small case study that shows the importance of providing EU funding for non-governmental organisations in Slovakia.

1. EU BUDGET

The EU budget is a combination of resources at the European level, the main aim of which is to promote growth and competitiveness at a broader European level. The EU budget is, in principle, an investment budget that complements EU national budgets and allows member states to achieve more than they could alone (European Union, 2021b).

At the EU level, a distinction is made between long-term and annual budgets. The purpose of the long-term budget is to set long-term priorities and constraints on EU spending, thus ensuring the effectiveness of EU policies. A long-term budgetary plan called the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) allows the EU to plan its funding programs several years in advance, usually seven

years. The MFF is the basis for determining expenditure and revenue for the annual budgets (European Union, 2021b).

The MFF is currently in force for 2021-2027, where the European Union has € 1,211 billion in funding at its disposal. In addition, during this programming period, the European Union will borrow € 806 billion through financial operations on the capital market and provide these funds to strengthen the economy and finance the adverse economic consequences of the COVID-19 crisis (MF SR, 2021; European Commission, 2021b).

1.1. Funding for NGOs

EU funding sources represent various types of funding: grants, financial instruments, subsidies, trust funds prizes and procurements. However, the most used form of funding for NGOs is a grant, representing the direct provision of EU budget funding for a specific NGO (European Commission, a). All conditions for applying for EU grants are published on the European Commission website as well as on the websites of local authorities since EU countries themselves primarily manage those funding sources. However, organisations applying for EU grants do not have to apply alone but can find a partner via the European Commission's portal and apply for a grant together (European Commission, h).

The main areas supported by EU funds are social inclusion, gender equality and equal opportunities, culture and media, foster citizenship and civic participation, research and innovation, development and humanitarian aid, transport, energy and ICT (European Commission, h).

The EU regularly publishes and updates lists of EU funding programmes, grouping them into so-called Headings, which essentially represent the spending categories of the EU budget.

1.2. Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps programmes

Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps (ESC), which will be analysed later in this paper, were selected for analysis because NGOs use them significantly (Publications Office of EU, 2020; Klymchuk, 2021; Tahmaz, 2021).

In the preceding 7-year budget period (2014-2020), the Erasmus+ and ESC programmes fell under Heading 1a: Competitiveness for growth and jobs, which focused on resources, education and infrastructure (European Commission, f). In the current 7-year budget period, the Erasmus+ and ESC programmes fall under Heading 2b: Resilience and values, with these programs making a significant

contribution to the policy area of Investing in people, social cohesion and values (European Parliament, 2021).

2. ERASMUS+ PROGRAMME

Erasmus+ is a European Union programme that supports people's educational, professional and personal development in education, training, youthwork and sport in Europe (European Commission, b; European Commission, e). Erasmus+ has been operating since 2014, but its predecessor programmes have been in place since 2007. Within this program, we are talking about the so-called seven-year lifecycle, for which its funding is set (European Commission, c)

Eligible applicants for an Erasmus+ grant are not only organizations but also individuals (European Commission, d). However, individuals wishing to apply for this grant must apply through the registered organization in which they work, study or volunteer. Also, the country where the applying organization is located is essential in terms of eligibility for the specific grant. The Erasmus+ Program recognizes the so-called program countries, containing all EU Member States and third countries associated with the Programme, which are subject to the Association Agreements between the EU and those countries. However, this program also distinguishes between third countries not associated with the Program, which may be involved in the Actions of the Programme if certain conditions are met.

2.1. Erasmus+ Programme statistics

In the current seven-year life cycle, € 26.51 billion has been earmarked for Erasmus+ Programme projects (European Commission, b).

From 2014 to 2020, more than € 16 billion was redistributed through the Erasmus+ programme. However, we took the liberty to look at the overall EU budget to quantify how much of the funding has been allocated to the Erasmus+ Programme. Based on available data, we found that the funds allocated to the Erasmus+ Programme represent the average annual expenditure of 1.5% (1.06%, 1.26%, 1.5%, 1.57%, 1.51%, 1.8% and 1.77%) of total EU expenditure. However, as the Erasmus+ Programme is part of the Smart and inclusive growth category, we also calculated that Erasmus+ Programme expenditure averages 11.5% (11.32%, 10.92%, 11.09%, 10.07%, 10.93%, 13.14% and 12.75%) of the total annual expenditure allocated to this category.

Between 2014 and 2020, there were 5 project areas under the Erasmus+ programme (see Figure 1), the so-called Key Actions, where more than € 10 billion flowed into KA1 - Learning Mobility Of Individuals projects, representing up to 64% of the total budget. The second most supported project area was KA2 projects - Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices, where 31.7% of the total budget was provided. The project areas where the allocated funds did not exceed 2% were KA3 - Support For Policy Reform and Erasmus+ Sports. The least supported area was the category Erasmus+ Jean Monnet, where the allocated funds did not represent even 1% of the total allocated budget.

Figure 1: Allocation of funds under the Erasmus+ Programme in 2014-2020

Source: own processing based on data from European Commission (c)

However, the differences are not only noticeable in the budgetary area but also in the number of projects submitted in the individual Key Actions. Under the Erasmus+ programme in 2014-2020, were submitted 159,952 project applications, with the most significant number, up to 81.1% (129,651) of all submitted projects being project applications for Key Action 1. The second most numerous category was Key Action 2, but these applications accounted for only 15.5% (24,806) of all submitted projects. The least represented Key Actions were KA3, Jean Monnet and Sports, which accounted for 1.5% (2,458), 1.2% (1,863) and 0.7% (1,174) of the total number of submitted projects.

The most successful categories in obtaining financial support under the Erasmus+ Programme were Key Actions Jean Monnet and Sports, where all projects were supported. KA2 achieved a 99.7% (24,741) success rate of funding, KA3 had a 99.1% (2,436) success rate of obtaining funds, and the least projects were supported from the submitted projects within KA1, namely 95.3% (123,549).

We also noticed (see Table 1) that within this 7-year lifecycle of the Erasmus+ Programme, the number of project submissions has been consistently growing. Annual increases in the number of submitted projects until 2019 ranged from 1,173-1,434 projects. However, there was a significant increase in submitted project applications in 2020, where the annual difference was an increase of up to 6916 project applications.

Table 1: Development of the number of projects within the Erasmus+ in 2014-2020

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Number of submitted projects	18,119	19,498	20,671	22,105	23,301	24,671	31,587
Number of supported projects	18,066	19,463	20,620	22,064	23,243	24,508	25,799

Source: own processing based on data from European Commission (c)

Within the framework of financing through the Erasmus+ Programme in the years 2014-2020, it is possible to observe a growing tendency in allocating funds in individual years (see Figure 2). We can also state that at the beginning of the implementation of the Erasmus+ Programme, i.e. in 2014, the projects were allocated 2.5 times less funding than in the year 2020. By 2018 the annual increases were in the range of € 199-286 million, and since then, the annual change has more than doubled.

Figure 2: Development of the allocated amount under the Erasmus+ in 2014-2020 in € million

Source: own processing based on data from European Commission (c)

2.2. Erasmus+ predecessor programmes statistics

Erasmus+ predecessor programmes were active from 2007-2013 when they were allocated more than € 468 million.

The most supported program during this period was Erasmus Mundus (see Figure 3), where more than € 255 million flowed, representing almost 55% of the total budget allocated to these programs. The second most supported program was the Life-Long Learning program, where almost 29% of the total budget was provided. The programs where the allocated funds did not exceed 10% were the remaining programs, namely the Youth in Action, Tempus and Sports programs, where 9.9%, 6.7% and 0.3% of the total funds were provided, respectively.

Figure 3: Allocation of funds under the Erasmus+ predecessor Programmes in 2007-2014

Source: own processing based on data from European Commission (c)

In total, 23,282 project applications were submitted from 2007-2013, of which only 12.8% (2,988) were supported. Life-Long Learning project applications accounted for 81.38% (2,988) of all project applications under these programs, but EU funds supported only 2.54% (482) of them. The second most numerous group of submitted projects, and thus 14.66% (3,413) of all submitted applications, were those for the Youth in Action program, while up to 69.35% (2,367) were supported. Tempus and Erasmus Mundus project applications accounted for 2.35% (547) and 1.58% (369) of all applications, respectively. The Erasmus Mundus program was more successful, with up to 25.47% (94) of projects supported, while in the Tempus programme it was 6.95% (38). The least represented program in the number of submitted project applications was the Sports program, whose applications represented only 0.03% of the total number of applications. Although the Sports program was the least represented in the

number of applications, it achieved the highest rate in the funded projects as all 7 projects were contracted. Another interesting feature of the Sports program is that all 7 project applications were submitted in 2013, i.e. in the last year of operation of this program.

3. ESC

The European Solidarity Corps is a European Union programme that funds volunteering and solidarity projects aimed at involving young people in tackling societal challenges. Spheres of solidarity here mean helping the disadvantaged, humanitarian aid or contributing to activities aimed at health and the environment. The program's ambition is greater inclusiveness, environmental friendliness, and digitization. ESC has been operating since late 2018 and is aimed at organizations in the EU and partner countries, as well as individuals aged 18 to 30 (European Commission, g).

3.1. ESC Programme statistics

During the pilot launch period, from autumn 2018, until the end of 2019, more than € 113 million was redistributed to 3,750 projects by the ESC programme (Publications Office of EU, 2020). Exact statistics on the redistribution of funds to individual action types are not published for 2020. However, in the current period, i.e. in the period 2021-2027, € 1.009 billion is earmarked for projects under the new European Solidarity Corps. (European Union, 2021a).

Based on the published information on the annual EU budgets, we can assess that the funds allocated for the ESC Programme in 2018-2020 averaged annual expenditures of 0.05% (0.02%, 0.07% and 0.08%) of total EU expenditures. However, as the ESC falls under the Competitiveness for growth and jobs category under the Smart and inclusive growth category, we also calculated that ESC expenditure accounts for an average of 0.39% (0.12%, 0.5% and 0.56%) of the total annual expenditure allocated to this category.

Within the ESC, there are 3 project areas, the so-called Action types - Traineeships and Jobs, Solidarity Projects and Volunteering. In 2018-2019, the support for Volunteering projects represented more than € 105 million, accounting for up to 93% (€ 105,633,466) of the total budget allocated to ESC. The second most supported area was Solidarity Projects, where 6% (€ 6,325,898) of the total budget was provided. The last, least supported type of project within

the ESC was Traineeships and Jobs, where the allocated funds did not exceed 1% (€ 1,439,767) of the total allocated budget.

In total, 5,042 project applications were submitted, of which 74% (3,750) were supported. Volunteering project applications accounted for 67% (3,396) of all project applications under these programme, and EU funds supported 79% (2,685) of them. The second most numerous group of submitted projects, representing 31% (1,540) of all submitted applications, were those for the Solidarity Projects, while up to 64% (984) of them were supported. The least represented action type in the number of submitted project applications was the Traineeships and Jobs, whose applications represented only 2% (106) of the total number of applications, but up to 76% (81) of them were funded.

4. SLOVAKIA

Slovakia has been a member of the EU since 2004 and is an eligible country to participate in grant calls under EU programmes. In this part of the paper, we looked at the use of Erasmus+ and ESC programmes in Slovakia and we also at the specific case of two non-governmental nonprofit organisations that operate in Slovakia and actively use these EU programmes.

4.1. Erasmus+ Programme

The use of Erasmus+ grants is becoming increasingly popular in Slovakia as well, as evidenced by the fact that in the first 7-year cycle of Erasmus+ projects, the amount of funding for these projects implemented in Slovakia increased every year (see Figure 4). We can also see that immediately after the launch of this Programme, there were only very slight increases in the amounts flowing to Slovakia, but since 2017 it is possible to observe more significant increases. The total amount of these funds for Slovakia added to almost € 214.3 million.

Figure 4: Development of the allocation of funds under the Erasmus+ in Slovakia in 2014-2020 in € million

Source: own processing based on data from European Commission (2021a)

Until 2020 Learning abroad projects were more financially supported than Cooperation projects, which also resulted from the number of contracted project applications for these types of projects (see Table 2). The change took place in 2020 when 134 Cooperation projects were allocated € 760,000 more than 317 Learning abroad projects. Such a significant change was also helped by the inability to travel abroad due to the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, as the number of project applications for Learning abroad decreased significantly in 2020 compared to the previous period and, conversely, applications to Cooperation projects almost doubled.

Table 2: Development of supported Erasmus+ projects per project type in 2014-2020

Project/partnership	Number of supported projects							
	TOTAL	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
TOTAL	3,077	327	376	415	459	474	535	491
Learning abroad	2,485	302	339	338	370	390	429	317
Cooperation projects	420	25	34	38	51	59	79	134

Source: own processing based on data from European Commission (2021a)

In addition to the projects already mentioned, the Erasmus+ Programme also supported development and cooperation in other areas, particularly in education (79) and sport (59). Less represented include Cooperation between higher education institutions and businesses (19), Social inclusion (12) and Erasmus Mundus (3).

4.2. ESC

Information on projects implemented through the ESC is only available for its pilot period 2018/2019, in which 131 project applications were submitted in

Slovakia, but only 79 were contracted. Of the supported project applications, 42 were Volunteering projects, 35 were Solidarity Projects and 2 were Traineeships and Jobs projects. The total grants contracted for Slovakia in this period amounted to more than € 1.3 million, with the largest part, up to 79% (€ 1,068,828), being allocated to the Volunteering projects. Grants provided for Solidarity Projects accounted for 16% (€ 212,316) of the total grants, and the least funding went to Traineeships and Jobs projects, just 6% (€ 76,814).

4.3. Case Study – Slovak NGO/NPO & Erasmus+ and ESC Programmes

In this part of the paper, we will focus on two nongovernmental non-profit organizations that operate in Slovakia and actively use the Erasmus+ grant calls. Both analysed organizations, EduEra and Change Your Self, are civic associations based in the east part of the country in the city of Košice. Also, both organizations work as a young people-led platform for young people, focusing on non-formal education. Those civic associations create opportunities and space for young people to become responsible, aware and exemplary young adults. They create opportunities for education through trainings, workshops, volunteering and projects not only in Slovakia but also abroad, thanks to the Erasmus+ program.

The difference between these organisations is the year of establishment, as EduEra was founded in April 2017 and Change Your Self in October 2018.

Based on the data provided by the civic associations EduEra & Change Your Self, we can see that in both organizations, the most significant part of the budget is the funds provided through the Erasmus+ Programme (see Table 3).

Table 3: Total revenues of EduEra and Change Yourself by revenue type

Income source	EduEra	Change Your Self
TOTAL	€ 390,834.82	€ 152,499.47
Membership fees	€ 190.10	€ 1,143.46
Erasmus+ grant	€ 378,091.26	€ 149,362.96
European Solidarity Corps (ESC)	€ 11,590.40	-
Eurodesk	€ 350.00	-
Active Citizens Fund (ACF)	€ 300.00	-

Assignment tax	€ 313.06	€ 393.05
Own financing	-	€ 1,600.00

Source: own processing based on data provided by the NGOs

For EduEra, Erasmus+ grants account for almost 97% of the organisation's total revenue, but all EU funding (Erasmus+, ESC and Eurodesk) accounts for up to 99.79% of total revenue. The remaining income items of EduEra do not exceed the value of 0.1%, namely revenues from ACF or assignment tax representing 0.08% of the budget and revenues from membership fees representing the least, 0.05% of the total revenues of the organisation.

For the civic association Change Your Self, Erasmus+ Programme revenues account for almost 98% of total revenues, but this civic association has not yet applied for grants from other EU programmes. An interesting item of the budget is the income from own activities, representing 1.05% of total revenues. Membership fees and the income from the Assignment tax in this organization do not exceed 1% of its income

In the case of EduEra, we can see (see Table 4) that apart from the year in which the organization was founded, the most significant revenue item is Erasmus+ grants. In the first two years of the organization's operation, membership fees were also a source of income. In 2020 the organization received a one-off reward from the Active Citizens Fund and, at the same time registered as an applicant for the assignment tax, which was received in 2021.

Table 4: Income of the EduEra in 2017-2021

Income source	Year				
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
TOTAL	€ 73.10	€ 42,409.00	€ 77,255.80	€ 148,530.20	€ 122,566.72
Membership fees	€ 73.10	€ 117.00	-	-	-
Erasmus+ grant	-	€ 42,292.00	€ 66,693.00	€ 146,852.60	€ 122,253.66
ESC	-	-	€ 10,212.80	€ 1,377.60	-
Eurodesk	-	-	€ 350.00	-	-

ACF	-	-	-	€ 300.00	-
Assignment tax	-	-	-	-	€ 313.06

Source: own processing based on data provided by the NGOs

In the case of the civic association Change Your Self, we can see a similar structure of funding sources across the years of its operation compared to EduEra (see Table 5). Revenue from Erasmus+ grants accounted for the largest share of the revenue of this organization in each year of operation, except for the year of its establishment. This organization also had income from membership fees during the first two years of operation and is also a recipient of allocation tax since 2019. A significant change in this organization's financing is its own source of funding in the last financial year, which was income for a series of workshops organized by the civic association Change Your Self for the organization in Azerbaijan.

Table 5: Income of the Change Your Self in 2018-2021

Income source	Year			
	2018	2019	2020	2021
TOTAL	€ 1,020.00	€ 72,660.68	€ 60,810.53	€ 18,008.26
Membership fees	€ 1,020.00	€ 123.46	-	-
Erasmus+ grant	-	€ 72,537.22	€ 60,584.34	€ 16,241.40
Assignment tax	-	-	€ 226.19	€ 166.86
Own financing	-	-	-	€ 1,600.00

Source: own processing based on data provided by the NGO

All the funds that EduEra and Change Your Self obtained through Erasmus+ were used to implement their successfully submitted projects. EduEra has successfully submitted 10 project applications under the Erasmus+ Programme (see Table 5), and in addition to these projects EduEra participates in many others as cobeneficiary.

Table 5: Funded Erasmus+ projects submitted by EduEra

Mobility Type	Year	Project Title
International expert seminar	2018	Let's get cross

International training course	2018	TRAINBOW
International youth exchange	2018	Spread The Word!
International training course	2019	Coaching: Level One, Quality Measures in the European Solidarity Corps
International expert seminar	2019	COLOURS OF YOUTH WORK
International training course	2020	DIGIBOX (edition 2020), PILLARS OF EMPOWERMENT
KA2 Strategic partnership	2020	AdultLife
KA2 Strategic partnership for creativity	2020	RECALIBUR

Source: own processing based on data provided by the NGO

Likewise, the organization Change Your Self acts in many projects as a cobeneficiary and has successfully submitted 9 project applications in the Erasmus+ Programme (see Table 6).

Table 6: Funded Erasmus+ projects submitted by Change Your Self

Mobility Type	Year	Project Title
International youth exchange	2017	Know Your Human Rights, War and Peace
International youth exchange	2018	Ambassadors of Tolerance
International youth exchange	2019	[DEMO]cracy, YOUth Brand – Make Yourself Employable!
International training course	2019	Start Pack for Youth Workers, Pour Faciliter 2020
Mobility of Youth Workers	-	Leaders of Future
Mobility of Youth Workers	-	Reflection

Source: own processing based on data provided by the NGO

The difference in obtaining funding for these two organizations, as mentioned above, is that EduEra applied for other EU funds in addition to applying for Erasmus+ grants. In 2018, EduEra submitted 3 successful project

applications (EduEgo a ID!; Vzdelávaj sa, Pomáhaj a Chráň! and Víta vás EduEra!) for Solidarity Projects. In addition to these implemented Solidarity Projects, EduEra also submitted other applications and plans to continue.

CONCLUSIONS

In Slovakia, as in many other European countries, the nonprofit sector is booming, and so is the need for its financing.

The EU and its programs are a major driving force for NGOs. In this paper, two selected EU programs were pointed out as demonstrable funding sources for the nonprofit world. Erasmus+ and ESC projects significantly impact the development of civil society and are the driving forces behind the required changes in society. Thanks to these programs, NGOs can educate and draw the attention of future generations to societal issues that need to be addressed. Through information on the results of EU budgeting and funds allocated to the two analysed EU programs, we could point out the ever-increasing amounts of grants provided for projects under Erasmus+ and ESC and the continuously increasing project applications submitted in these grant calls. Likewise, the two analysed Slovak NGOs confirm our assumption that Slovakia has quality non-governmental, nonprofit organisations. However, they struggle to ensure an effective model of financing their activities, as more than 97% of their annual income is from EU grants. Although these organisations are eager for new grant calls, this type of funding is not sustainable in the long run, as the period associated with the Covid-19 pandemic has shown. Although these organisations actively use grants provided by the EU for non-governmental and nonprofit organisations, they still bear the consequences of the recent pandemic, as many of their projects have had to be extended or postponed until the present without additional funding.

Further research could focus on other EU programs that help develop civic participation, including providing funding to nonprofit entities. A comprehensive case study focusing on specific types of nonprofit organizations and project applications submitted by them for EU programs could also be beneficial. Such a study could help to make cooperation between equally oriented nonprofit organizations more effective, whether within a single country or at the European level.

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